

Comparison of Two Methods of Relativistic Corrections to the Wavefunction

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The bound state one-dimensional Dirac equation may be written in terms of two functions, $u(x)$ and $v(x)$. In the nonrelativistic limit, the equation for $u(x)$ reduces to the Schrodinger equation. In a previous note, we attempted to calculate a relativistic correction to $u(x)$ which was found to be $(1/(e^*e-V^*V) - 1/(2m)) (d/dx V) (d/dx u_0) + (e+V)/2m u_0$, where u_0 is the Schrodinger wavefunction and e is the nonrelativistic energy $E-m$. (m =rest mass). This result, may then be used to evaluate a correction to the energy e .

In a recent result from the literature (from 2013) (1), a different approach is taken. A new kinetic energy operator is calculated from the Dirac equations with no potential present. It is found to be:

$$t = m \left[\sqrt{1 + 2t_0/m} - 1 \right] \quad \text{where } c=1 \text{ and } t_0 = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \quad ((1))$$

where $t_0 = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$. Next, it is suggested the nonrelativistic equation is: $[t_0 + V(x)] W(x) = E_{nr} W(x)$ and the relativistic $[t + V(x)] = E_r W(x)$. Perturbation theory is then used to calculate a relativistic correction to E_{nr} i.e. $\langle t - t_0 \rangle$ where the Schrodinger equation wavefunctions are used in the calculation.

The results of the two methods are very similar and yield the same $1/2m$ order of magnitude corrections to the Schrodinger energy. There are, however, some differences. As a result, the objective of this note is to compare the two.

Kinetic Energy Operator Approach of (1)

In this approach, a kinetic energy operator is obtained from the coupled Dirac equations with no potential present. In such a case, $p = -i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ in the Dirac equation, but $t = E - m$. (m =rest mass). The result is found to be (see details in (1)):

$$t = m \left[\sqrt{1 + 2t_0/m} - 1 \right] \quad \text{where } c=1 \text{ and } t_0 = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \quad ((1))$$

This seems to be based on $E u = (t + m) u$ and the Einstein energy momentum relationship: $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ with $p = -i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$.

This result is then expanded as a power series in $1/2m$ yielding:

$$t = t_0 \left[1 - \frac{t_0}{2m} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{t_0}{2m} \right)^2 + \dots \right] \quad ((2))$$

The authors then proceed to apply this kinetic energy operator to the Schrodinger equation. They compare:

$$[t_0 + V(x)] W(x) = E_n W(x) \text{ with } [t_0 + V(x)] W(x) \quad ((3))$$

The difference in the Hamiltonians is t_0 and this is used in perturbation theory to calculate a correction to the Schrodinger equation energy i.e.:

$\langle t_0 \rangle$ where the Schrodinger equation wavefunction is used. Several examples are given.

One example involves an infinite potential for $r \geq d$ and $V=0$ for $r < d$. The Schrodinger energy for this case is shown to be:

$$E_n = \frac{m}{2} (n\pi)^2 \left(\frac{1}{md} \right)^2 \text{ which goes as } 1/m. \quad ((4))$$

and the correction:

$$\langle t_0 \rangle = m \left[\sqrt{1 + 2 \langle t_0 \rangle / 2m} - 1 - \langle t_0 \rangle / m \right] \quad ((5))$$

Given that there is no potential for $r < d$, $\langle t_0 \rangle = E_n$.

Expanding ((5)) shows the relativistic correction is of order $1/(m^3 m)$. The authors of ((1)) show it is a 1% corrections for some numbers, but suggest that for a nucleon in a nucleus, the correction is appreciable (for $n=1$).

Wavefunction Correction Method

In (2), a relativistic correction is calculated to $u(x)$, the function of Dirac equations which becomes the Schrodinger wavefunction in the nonrelativistic limit. The Klein Gordon equation is also used in obtaining this correction as the following is used:

$$(E^2 - m^2) (u_0 + u_a) = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (u_0 + u_a) \text{ or } (E^2 - m^2) u_a = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} u_a \quad ((6))$$

This result is combined with the Dirac equations in one dimension:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \frac{1}{(E+m+V)} \frac{d}{dx} u(x) \right\} = (E-m-V) u(x) \quad ((7))$$

to yield, after a number of cancellations:

$$u_a = \frac{1}{(E^2 - m^2 - V^2)} \frac{1}{(2m)} \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} u_0 \right) + \frac{(E+V)}{2m} u_0$$

Here u_0 is the Schrodinger wavefunction. It is argued that u_a may be used to calculate a correction to the nonrelativistic energy level. In (1), perturbation theory is used to yield the correction as:

$\langle \text{difference in } H \rangle = \langle t - t_0 \rangle$

where the nonrelativistic wavefunction is used.

Here, we suggest using:

$$\langle u_0 + u_a | h_0 + h_{\text{extra}} | u_0 + u_a \rangle - \langle u_0 | h_0 | u_0 \rangle \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{or } \langle u_0 | h_{\text{extra}} | u_0 \rangle + 2\langle u_0 | h_0 | u_a \rangle + \langle u_a | h_0 | u_a \rangle \quad ((9))$$

At first, $\langle u_0 | h_{\text{extra}} | u_0 \rangle$ appears to be the leading term. From the results of (1), this term is calculated as $O(1/(m^*m^*m))$ for a potential of $V(x)=0$ $r < d$ $V(x)=\text{infinite}$ $r > d$. From (2), however, one has:

$$e(e+V)/2m \langle u_a | u_a \rangle = e^*e/2m \quad (1) \quad \text{and } e \text{ goes as } 1/m \text{ so the result is } O(1/(m^*m^*m)) \quad ((10))$$

We ignore $d/dx V(x)$.

Thus, the corrections are of the same order. One must still calculate $2\langle u_0 | h_{\text{extra}} | u_0 \rangle$ for (2). From results shown below for h_{extra} for method (2), one may see that it is also of order $O(1/(m^*m^*m))$.

In (1), a three dimensional oscillator is considered. There, the correction is of the order $w^*w/2m$ where $w = \sqrt{k/m}$. For $\langle u_0 | h_0 (e+V)/2m | u_0 \rangle$ one also obtains an order of $w^*w/2m$.

Thus, to compare the two methods one needs to go further. One must also consider the situation of the "extra h". In (1) it is given by $t - t_0$, as the "relativistic" correction Hamiltonian is:

$$[t+V] u(x) = E_r u(x) \quad ((11)) \quad \text{or} \quad t_0 [1 - t_0/2m + \frac{1}{2} (t_0/2m)^2] u(x) = E_r u(x) \quad \text{from } ((2)). \quad ((11))$$

Expanding ((7)), however, yields:

$$(1/2m)[1 - (e+V)/2m + ((e+V)/2m)^2] \{-d/dx d/dx u\} + (d/dx u) [- (d/dx V) / (2m^*2m) + 2(e+V) (d/dx V) / (2m^*2m^*2m)] = (e-V) u \quad ((12))$$

One may see that ((12)) contains derivatives of V which do not ever seem to appear in ((11)).

For simplicity, let us compare ((11)) and ((12)) for the case of $V=0$ inside $r < d$ and $t_0 u(x) = e u(x)$.

Then: ((11)) becomes: $t_0 u(x) - (1/2m) e^*e u(x) + \frac{1}{2} (1/2m)(1/2m) e^*e^*e u(x) = e u(x)$ where $E_r = e$.

For ((12) on has: $\hat{t} u(x) - (1/2m) \hat{e}^* \hat{e} u(x) + (1/2m) \hat{e}^* \hat{e} / (2m) \hat{e} u(x) = \hat{e} u(x)$

A more general comparison can be made, replacing: $\hat{t} u = (e-V)u$ to first order. Then, ((11)) becomes:

$$\hat{t} u + \left\{ -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} V \right\} u / (2m^*2m) - (e-V)(e-V) u / 2m - 2 \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} u \right) / (2m^*2m) \right\} = (e-V) u \quad ((13))$$

While ((12) becomes:

$$\hat{t} u + (e+V) / (2m^*2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} u - \left(\frac{d}{dx} u \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) / (2m^*2m) = (e-V) u$$

$$\text{Or } \hat{t} u - (e+V)(e-V) / (2m) - \left(\frac{d}{dx} u \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) / (2m^*2m) = (e-V) u$$

((14))

Thus, \hat{h} extra for the method of (2) is: $-(e+V)(e-V) / (2m) - \left(\frac{d}{dx} u \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) / (2m^*2m)$

For the method of (1), it is: $\hat{t} - \hat{t}_0 = \hat{t}_0 \left(\frac{\hat{t}_0}{2m} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hat{t}_0}{2m} \right)^2 \right) = \left\{ -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} V \right\} u / (2m^*2m) - (e-V)(e-V) u / (2m^*2m) - 2 \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} u \right) / (2m^*2m) \right\}$.

These equations are similar, but not exact. For example ((13)) contains a $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} V$ term which is not present in ((14)). In addition, the term with $\left(\frac{d}{dx} u \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right)$ differs by a factor of 2 between the two. Furthermore, one method has $(e+V)(e-V)$ while the other $(e-V)(e-V)$. This differences do not change order of magnitude results, it seems.

Thus, first of all, for the method of (2), $u = u_0 + u_b$ while for the method of (1) only u_0 is used. Secondly, $\hat{h} - \hat{h}_0$ is different for the two methods as the equations above are slightly different.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have attempted to compare two methods for dealing with relativistic corrections to the Schrodinger equation. The first defines a new kinetic energy operator in powers of $1/2m$ ($-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$), but does not consider changes to the Schrodinger eigenfunctions when calculating energy level shifts i.e. $\hat{e}_0 + \langle \hat{t} - \hat{t}_0 \rangle$ (with the Schrodinger equation eigenfunctions used).

The second method considers a change to the Schrodinger eigenfunctions of the form: $\left(\frac{1}{(e^* e - V^* V)} \frac{1}{(2m)} \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} u_0 \right) + (e+V)/2m u_0 \right)$.

In addition, relativistic equations, keeping only a few $1/2m$ expansion terms are similar for the two models, but not exactly the same. Thus, “h extra” for the two methods are slightly different. The two methods seem to give very similar energy shifts.

References

1. Kamuntavicius, Gintautus, Basic Quantum Hamiltonian's Relativistic Corrections (2013)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1302.0491.pdf>
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